

ISic2876

I.Sicily inscription 2876

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 13978

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334897

1. ἐκοιμήθη ἔ [ν] π[ί]σ [τι καὶ]
2. ἠρήνη ἢ δούλη τοῦ
3. θ (εο) ὤ Πρόβα ὄσσαρία ²⁶ὄστιαρία²⁶
4. □ α τῆς ἀγίας καὶ καθο-
5. ληκῆς ἐκκλησίας Λιπ-
6. ἀρέων· τελευτᾷ ἐτῶν κ'
7. πρὸ μιᾶς κ[α]λαδῶν ²⁶καλανδῶν²⁶ Σεπτεβρίω [ν] ²⁶Σεπτεμβρίων²⁶.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645270
PHI 334897

Bibliography

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